

DELIVERABLE

Project Acronym: Q-SORT
Grant Agreement number: 766970
Project Title: Q-SORT. The Quantum Sorter: A New Measurement Paradigm in Electron Microscopy

Manuscript for paper on implementation of new phase elements in TEM

D2.6

Version 1.0

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Project funded by the European Commission within the FET OPEN Programme		
Dissemination Level		
P	Public	X
C	Confidential, only for members of the consortium and the Commission Services	

Revision History

Revision	Date	Author	Organisation	Description
0.1	3/06/19	V. Grillo	CNR	First Draft
0.2	12/06/19	S.Frabboni A. Tavabi P. Rosi P. Lu E. Karimi G. Pozzi R. E Dunin Borkowski A.Roncaglia P. Tjiemajer	UMR FZJ UMR U. Ottawa FZJ FZJ CNR FEI CNR FZJ	Feedback on the text and typo correction
0.3	13/06/19	E. Rotunno	CNR	Suggestion to add supplementary material
0.4	17/06/19	V. Grillo	CNR	Supplementary material added
0.5	24/06/19	P. Rosi	UMR	Correction of experimental details
1.0	28/06/19	V. Grillo	CNR	Final version

Statement of originality:

This deliverable contains original unpublished work except where clearly indicated otherwise. Acknowledgement of previously published material and of the work of others has been made through appropriate citation, quotation or both.

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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

This deliverable is the final result of WP2 marking the realization of a working sorter device. The completion of this device marks the realization of Milestone M6 and the progress in the realization of WP4 and part of WP5.

The deliverable is written in the form of paper describing the main results.

The main part of the text of the paper is divided in Introduction, Experimental setup, Sorter in practice, results, Effect of the astigmatism correction electrodes, Phase of sorter 2, conclusions.

The main aim of the first 3 sections is to explain the setup of the sorter and its working mode. The second part is instead concentrated on what can be still improved or anyway important details that really matter for the final resolution of the device.

In addition we added a large supplementary section partially copied by the previous deliverable. This material would be strongly necessary as the paper is now very technical

Finally we added the comment of two internal reviewer and our response to that.

EXPERIMENTAL DEMONSTRATION OF ELECTROSTATIC OAM SORTER

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ABSTRACT:

We show here the first demonstration of a new electro-optical device called electron Orbital Angular Momentum (OAM) sorter that permits to analyze the OAM state of electrons. It is based on a few modifications of the electron microscopy column with the introduction of 2 new electrostatic elements. We calibrated the sorter with a few standard inline holograms and found that the OAM-sorter successfully produces an OAM spectrum with resolution of $\Delta L_z = 2 \hbar$. This can be further improved by a better control of the new sorting phase elements.

INTRODUCTION

The electron microscopy has delivered in the past years impressing results in terms of analysis of materials accessing sub Å resolution [1], 3D information [2] and few meV energy resolution [3].

This incredible performance of microscopy has hardly any comparison with the other instrument development. The key to this success is the improved capacity to control mechanically and electronically the electron magnetic field on the very local scale. The revolution introduced by the aberration correctors [4-8] has, for example, permitted to image single atoms and is an extraordinary masterpiece of engineering since the magnetic field of the two main hexapoles lenses must be matched, in intensity and position, in order to exactly compensate the aberrations.

For this reason, the realization of a working Cs Corrector has followed a long time since its initial theoretical ideation. Along these lines of progress we are proving here experimentally the realization of the first electrostatic analyzer for electrons that permits to separately analyze the electron orbital angular momentum [9-11] components.

As in the case of the above lensing devices, the correct functioning of the OAM sorter requires a perfect alignment and phase matching of the special lenses in the microscope and therefore a complicated effort of manufacture, control and understanding.

The OAM sorter has a somehow interesting similarity with an aberration corrector where two special lenses have to be matched in position and lens strength and to be located in two opposite lens planes .

Whereas in a previous work we already addressed the realization of such a device based on SiN holographic phase plates to that impart the necessary phase to the electron beam [11], here we demonstrate a completely electrostatic field-based device.

The difficulties in the realization of this device are those of a complete new electro-optic configuration, but this need to be somehow retrofitted into a working microscope with a reduced modification of the hardware. Still the effort for designing and realizing this new custom configuration was considerable.

This effort is repaid by the realization of a device that should allow a new set of measurements of otherwise difficult access. Applications are foreseen in EMCD [12], Cryo-microscopy [13], plasmonic [14], magnetic analysis of nanoparticles [10], as the introduction of a new degree of freedom in the analysis system is opening a new world in microscopy.

Most of these applications would have been not possible in the case of the holographic solutions since such a device strongly reduces the intensity of the beam.

In this work we will describe the technical steps that were required to produce such device and the results demonstrating the successful device up to the acquisition of the first OAM spectra in a microscope.

EXPERIMENTAL SETUP

An electron microscope with an electron sorter is, in appearance, very different from a normal microscope. The use of the sorter phase elements produces a conformal transformation from Cartesian to polar coordinates on the electron beam: the symmetry of the microscope is altered and the rotation, magnification and positioning between elements must be perfectly controlled. All of this seems to be worth a new design of the microscope. In reality, a simple addition of phase elements to replace pre-existing apertures of the microscope and a smart use of the microscope deflectors are sufficient to produce the new configuration while leaving the rest of the microscope nearly unaltered.

Figure 1 shows the configuration of the FEI Titan HOLO where the positions of the aperture and their predicted effect on the beam is illustrated.

Fig1 Scheme of the electrostatic sorter (a) and its position inside a FEI-TITAN HOLO (b)

The sample is located in the standard sample position in the objective lenses, the first sorter element S1 is located in the objective aperture plane while the second element is in the selected area (SAD) aperture position (the HOLO has two such apertures and for this experiment we used the first). So, the second sorter element S2 is in the diffraction plane of the first sorting element but in a plane conjugate to the sample. As a result of this configuration, the OAM spectrum is visible when the microscope is put in diffraction mode.

For testing reasons, we also introduced a SiN hologram in the condenser aperture plane producing, similar to those introduced in a previous paper [10], beams with well-defined OAM to be used as a test.

The sorting elements S1 and S2 are introduced in the electronic column through special custom aperture holder that permit to host, aside of normal diaphragms, an exchangeable MEMS chip with 8 contacts that can be connected, through the holder itself, to an external power supply.

According to the standard theory [9], the sorter element S1 should be a single, possibly very long, needle located in front of an electrostatic mirror. The theory predicts a needle as a straight line in the case of constant charge approximation or an ellipsoid for a fixed potential case. This is more realistic as tested also in Supp mat. Therefore we shaped by FIB milling the needles as ellipsoids.

In addition, two lateral needles have been also added, in agreement with our recent calculations [14], in order to compensate for the finite length of the wire. In facts such non-ideal electrode would otherwise induce an astigmatism that would undermine the OAM spectrum.

Since every lens induces a rotation, we have put particular attention in the orientation of the elements with respect to each other and to the entrance of the GIF interferometer.

For standard working condition we assumed a rotation of $\sim 23^\circ$ between objective aperture (OBJ-aperture) and the first SAD aperture (SAD1) and of $\sim 26^\circ$ between Objective (OBJ) aperture and the second SAD aperture (SAD2, in this case not used) that is present only in the special design of Titan HOLO. A SEM image of the actual devices are shown in fig 2. The MEMS chips have been produced by optical lithography starting from a doped Silicon wafer and further shaped in the 3rd dimension by FIB to produce the required electrode shape.

Fig2 SEM image of the electrodes for electrostatic S1 (a) and S2 (b) and relative schemes (c) and (d). The color coded are consistent with table 1.

SORTING IN PRACTICE

In order to test the microscope in Sorting mode we used a 2.6 mrad probe focused on the sample plane. The probe is then as large as roughly 20 µm in diameter in the OBJ aperture plane. The central needle of S1 is then mechanically positioned about the center of the beam. The movement of the element are actuated by the same motor used for conventional apertures.

In the image plane the diffraction of Sorter 1 appears as a rectangle roughly aligned to the Sorter 2 array. A small tuning of the corrector ADL lens can be used to fine tune the rotation while a variation of the voltage in S1 changes the lateral extension of the rectangle. Finally, after a rough mechanical alignment of the rectangular beam with S2 a fine tuning is performed using the image shift coils.

A switch of the lenses to diffraction mode permits to see the OAM spectrum directly on the screen, or using the GIF camera, to increase the magnification.

When in this mode a precise alignment of the beam shift is used to minimize the size of the diffraction and obtain a spectrum composed by a single line.

The actual voltages for sorter 1 and 2 are listed here in Table 1.

	S1 central (yellow)	S1 lateral (light blue)	S2 lateral (red)	S2 odd (blue)	S2 even (green)
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Applied Voltage (V)	-9.1	4.8	-8	-16	16
Number of electrodes	1	2	2	4	5

RESULTS

As previously mentioned, in order to estimate the OAM resolution we inserted the special condenser aperture containing an inline hologram producing a combination of OAM states that can be used as calibration of the spectrometer.

The main example is the vortex beam that we will call here L10. Even if this is programmed to be an exact vortex beam, imprecisions in the thickness control and amplitude effects introduces spurious harmonics in the OAM spectrum. If the S1 element is perfectly centered in the beam, the beam is then written as a combination

$$|\psi\rangle = \sum_{n=-\infty}^{+\infty} a_{10n} |10 \cdot n\rangle$$

This means that ideally any component that is not a multiple of 10 is actually due to the poor OAM resolution. In reality, a small effect due to the obstruction of the sorter tip is to be considered.

Figure 3 shows transformation of the wavefunction from the OBJ-aperture plane to the SAD and to the final OAM spectrum.

Fig 3 Evolution of the wavefunction with a nominal superposition of $|\ell=10\rangle$ and $|\ell=0\rangle$ from its generation (a) to its conformal transformation to polar coordinates (b) to its final transformation into an OAM spectrum(c).

It can be appreciated that, due to the finite size of the S1 tip, a part of the beam is indeed obstructed. As anticipated the effect of the obstruction is the introduction of a blurring in the OAM spectrum. Still simulation show that this produces a negligible broadening and spurious intensities below 5% on each neighboring channel.

We then evaluated the OAM spectrum and found a resolution of about 2h FWHM

Fig 4 Experimental OAM spectrum for 3 test beams with the nominal OAM composition described in caption.

This result is interesting because it demonstrates that a very simple procedure can still produce the relatively correct phase alignment necessary to achieve OAM decomposition. This result is

better than what obtained for the holographic approach that, before offline deconvolution for the Point spread function, showed a FWHM of $\sim 2.5\hbar$.

This result is, at the moment, worse than what expected from simulation based on measured phase of typical sorting elements as in Supp Mat 2. However these results are obtained based on a test of electrostatic phase elements in sample position where holography is used to directly test the phase and the voltage of the electrodes can be fine-tuned to obtain the desired phase. This is not possible at the moment in real experimental conditions since the phase elements are in the OBJ or SAD apertures. We can only indirectly or broadly check the results.

In the remaining of the paper we briefly overview the electrostatic parameters that we controlled and that need potentially further refining in order to obtain a better resolution.

EFFECT OF THE ASTIGMATISM CORRECTION ELECTRODES

According to the previously developed theory [14], lateral needles should be placed on the two sides of the S1 main needle at a voltage $V_L = -0.5V_C$. In order to test the working mode of these needles we changed systematically the voltage V_L ; the voltage of V_C was also slightly modified in order to keep the same S1 diffraction size.

Fig 5 Experimental OAM spectrum for the beam superposition of $|\ell=-10\rangle$ and $|\ell=0\rangle$ as a function of the voltage of the lateral electrodes of S1

The results are shown in fig 5, that clearly shows that the optimal OAM spectrum is obtained for $V_L = -0.5V_C$. This result highlight the importance of the lateral needles as a form of astigmatism correction. This result was expected based on fixed charge theory and confirmed by Finite Element simulations in Supp Mat. but still it is considerable that the optimal voltage is correctly predicted by the analytical approach. It is also a sign that the electrodes have been correctly shaped.

PHASE OF SORTER 2

The sorter element S2 is also problematic and when it is in the microscope in SAD2 it is very difficult to test the generated field. The present version of the sorter element S2 features 11 electrodes and this is about the limit that can be reached with the planar MEMS technology and 8 contacts.

Using the Transport of Intensity Equation (TIE) method [15] we produced a measurement of the phase that highlights at least some of the main feature of the phase. Even if the details of the phase are not perfectly reliable due to the limits of the technique (especially on boundary conditions) we can observe a quick damping of the phase oscillation even in the center due to the finite number of electrodes. This implies that the beam should be kept close to the electrodes.

Unfortunately, the beam also feels the imperfection of the electrodes shape (for example the small asymmetry of the tip toward right). This means that there is also a small range of distances that works well. Once the optimal distance from the electrodes is identified, the voltage of each electrode should be selected accordingly.

Fig 6 TIE evaluation of the phase about the electrostatic sorter element S2. Due to the limited field of view the uncertainty on the boundary condition are large. However it can be appreciated that part of the phase is distorted for ideal periodic distribution due to the limited number of electrodes.

CONCLUSIONS

To conclude we have demonstrated the first experimental realization of the electrostatic electron OAM sorter. The device is based on MEMS devices mounted in the Objective and SAD aperture of a microscope and connected to external electrostatic generators.

The OAM spectrum in the end has been obtained through thorough and tedious rotation, position and magnification alignment between electrostatic phase elements.

The device has been tested using SiN in-line holograms to produce beams with well-defined multiple of the original azimuthal frequency. Using such holograms the sorter resolution has been measured as $\sim 2\hbar$ FWHM, this value, whereas not optimal, can be potentially improved with a fine tuning of the single electrodes voltages in both Sorter elements.

In particular the astigmatism compensation in the S1 element and the tuning of boundary conditions in the S2 elements have a large improvement of the final resolution.

Simulations based on measured experimental suggest that a fine tuning and positioning could lead to a resolution of $1\hbar$ within reasonable conditions.

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ANNEX II: SUPPLEMENTARY MATERIAL

S1 MEMS design

Fig S1

The figure above shows the design of the masks for MEMS devices for the OAM sorter. It can be appreciated in the large scale image the area of the pads for contacting to the external of the holder. In the magnified image we evidenced the electrodes region. Electrodes that are kept to the same potential are indicated with the same colors. For convention in the rest of the text the electrodes of the sorter are named "lateral" (red) , "even" (Blue), "odd" (green) for sorter S2, and central (yellow) and lateral (bright blue) for the sorter S1.

Notice that in the element S2 thanks to a smart use of circuits we could address 11 electrodes + ground with 8 contacts still preserving the simplicity of the planar geometry.

S2 test of the best expected performance.

We characterized an early version of the sorter phase hologram with nominally worse specifications in order to assess the "best performance" of the sorter with realistic fields.

Therefore using electron holography we measured the phase of waves about the tips. The results are shown in fig S2.

Fig S2 Experimental phase measured for early prototypes of S1 and S2.

In order to simulate the experiment we made sure that the diffraction of Sorter1 matched in size the active area of Sorter2. Using then an alignment algorithm of STEMCELL we were able to find the most concentrate diffraction. This condition is what is also used in real experiments where the two elements are aligned by checking the actual OAM spectrum.

Mathematically the operation of alignment can be written as

$$\Psi(x, y) = \text{IFT}(\text{FT}(S1(x, y) \cdot P(x, y)) \cdot T_{\Delta u, \Delta v}(S2(u, v)))$$

P is the probe to be sorted (in this case just a constant) FT and IFT represent the direct and inverse Fourier Transform , T the translation operation necessary for alignment and the factors $S1(x, y) = \exp(i\varphi_1(x, y))$

$$S2(u, v) = \exp(i\varphi_2(u, v))$$

represent the effect of the sorter phase elements.

Figure S3 shows indeed (a) Sorter 1 diffraction calculated from experimental data in S2, (b) the Sorter2 experimental phase (c) the resulting phase after the alignment (d) the final spectrum . Since there was no structure in the original beam the spectrum peak should correspond to the OAM=0 condition. Unfortunately we can see in fig S3.c that the phase is still not completely stationary. This is an indication that some part of the sorter is not perfectly aligned possibly due to imperfections present at that time.

Fig S3 Simulated sorting experiment using experimental phases of sorter 1 & 2 . The diffraction of sorter1 (a) is superimposed to Sorter2(b) and after the alignment the wave in(c) is diffracted to a single line (d).

Fig S4 Simulation of alignment procedure based on OAM spectrum inspection and based on experimental phases of sorter1 &2: varying the relative position of the sorter1 and 2 we can obtain a very localized peak in the ideal case. In this case the peak is still quite narrow.

The series of figure S4 shows the alignment procedure that slowly brings from an image of the beam in the sorter plane to the OAM spectrum through a successive alignment that aims at the smaller OAM spectrum.

In order to test the resolution of the full sorter configuration we also used a petal beam ($L=\pm 5$) and the experimental phase as above trying to obtain by iterative alignment the best resolution.

The results are shown below. The alignment, orientation and magnification are done visually (looking at the OAM spectrum) as in experiments and we find that the spectrum still allows for a very good separation of the peaks at $L=\pm 5$. This also permits to calculate the OAM standard deviation as $0.96 \hbar$

Fig S5 Simulated spectrum with experimental phases for a petal beam $L=\pm 5$.

The spectral lines are not perfectly straight and the peaks side-lobes are among the most evident defects. Still we find that if an accurate control of the phase is carried on, through the control of each electrodes and a direct observation of the phase, the resolution can be improved easily by a factor 2. All these operations are done when the MEMS is in sample position, we still need to find a method to carry on the experiment when MEMS are in the OBJ and SAD positions.

S3 tip shape

The idea of sorter1 with the astigmatism correction given by lateral needle is somehow too simplified.

The analytical model above assumed fixed charge for the needle and the use of a mirror in front of the main needle.

In our case, this configuration is not completely realistic for the following reasons:

- What we do is actually controlling the voltage and not the charge in the electrodes. The actual shape of the electrodes and the induction can considerably modify the charge distribution with respect to the ideal case.
- The large electrode in front of the tip is actually as thick as the tip itself. This implies that we cannot assume it is a perfect charge mirror as in the analytical model above.

To gauge the effects of these deviation from the ideal sorter we decided to use Finite element simulations.

The COMSOL Software uses a realistic description of the MEMS geometry and the therefore account for these effects. It solves the 3D Dirichlet electrostatic problem of the biased conductor including any mutual induction.

The finite elements is a numerical method so normally we lose the predictive value of an analytical calculation. However even before using the numerical methods we were already able to predict an interesting effect in actual devices:

If the tip thickness is uniform the charge will tend to concentrate toward the tip.

If this is true, a simplified toy model would be to assume the charge as a uniform distribution (as in the ideal device) plus a concentrated charge at the tip.

The main effect of such charge is to add a phase superimposed to the sorting potential

$$\varphi = \varphi_0 \ln(|\vec{r} - \vec{r}_0|)$$

This is a sort of logarithmic focusing of the beam before sorting.

For the tip we used 3 types of geometry that are shown in the figures below.

Briefly, we can describe the tips as parallelepiped (a), elliptical cylinder (b) and ellipsoid (c).

The relevant projected potential for each configuration are shown in fig s6 d,e,f.

Fig S6 Geometry of the electrodes and total phase for sorter1 for different shape of the tip

The results of the calculation were exported as values of the potentials (a 1024 x 1024 x 100 pts grid) written in an ascii text file.

This grid of potential value per each point was then fed into a software that converts the grid of values of the potentials (written in the text file) into an image that is just the 2D map of the sum of the potential along z.

In fact what matters for us is only the phase acquired by the electron in each point that is

$$\phi(x, y) \propto \int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} V(x, y, z) dz$$

that we approximate to an integral in the region of the Finite element calculation extending for about 100 μm above and below the device.

The apparently smooth phase landscape resulting from these simulations is still not appropriate for checking the sorting properties.

In fact, the finite elements calculation intrinsically involves a discontinuity on derivatives. This is due to the simulation scheme that solves, for the electrostatic potential, the laplacian equation of electrostatic separately in each subdomains in which the volume of simulation is divided. It then connects continuously (but with discontinuous derivative) the solution for each domain. This creates a set of jumps in the derivatives every time a border between subdomains is encountered.

Since the sorting is based on diffracting the wave in a position determined by the local gradient of the sorter phase, these discontinuity in the derivative produce an artificial degradation of the solution.

We, therefore, applied a further elaboration of the projected potential map taking advantage of the fact that the phase must be $\nabla_{x,y}^2 \varphi = 0$ everywhere outside the tips.

Therefore, we applied the following filtering procedure

- Calculate the $\nabla_{x,y}^2 \varphi$,
- Apply a mask, where $\nabla^2 \varphi = \rho$ if $|\rho| < \varepsilon$ put $\rho = 0$
- Calculate inverse laplacian (through Fourier transforming)

This approach permits to generate smoother, and therefore more realistic, description of the sorting effect with almost no discontinuity in the derivatives.

Assuming now that the 3 phase landscape shown in fig s6 are correctly calculated we need to study which one is more similar to the theoretical image.

For the sake of comparison, below we plotted the theoretical case of $A=5$ $B=1.5$. These parameters have been selected by visual inspection to be more close to the set of parameters reachable by the electrostatic device.

Fig S7 Phase of an ideal sorter.

We can note both the similarities and differences between the realistic phase landscapes calculated by finite elements in fig s6 and the ideal sorter1 phase in fig s7.

Depending on the parameters there are indeed a round tip and straight lateral parts. The straight lateral parts are visible in all 3 configurations in fig 3 so it is difficult to understand which one is preferable.

In order to understand this differences, we must analyze the diffraction

Now the actual size of the sorter1 diffraction is bound to fit to the size of sorter 2 period.

Since the size of sorter2 is fixed by the geometry the increase of the parameter A must be compensated by a different excitation of the lenses, in particular a smaller focal length of the overall lens system. This must be well kept in mind during the experiment,

Fig S8 Diffraction of a petal beam ($L=+/-5$) impinging on 3 different sorter1 tip: rectangular (a), elliptical cylinder (b), ellipsoid (c).

For the simulation we just need to multiply the phase by a large scale factor. We therefore used a relatively large factor to test the effects of the different tips.

The figure shows the effect of the different tip shape on the sorter1 diffraction when a petal beam ($L=\pm 5$) is superimposed to the sorter.

The tips produce a different form of bending of the diffraction. Apparently the ellipsoid that is the most correct shape, produces the most straight line.

As anticipated the interpretation would be that the logarithmic focusing term due to charge accumulation on the tip produces a sort of artificial focusing.

Of course the tapering of the electrodes in the ellipsoid electrodes seem to act as a better counter-balance of this charge accumulation.

ANNEX III: REVIEW

Rev1: The results are really incredible considering that this is the first time such a device is mounted inside the microscope. Still I hope the resolution will improve in future experiments. How do you plan to improve the resolution?

The main problem seems to be in S2 so we will find a way to directly image the phase and make it similar to the ideal one in order to improve the result.

If this failed we could also consider doing an automatic control of the electrodes through PC with a feedback given by the spectra itself. We will need an automatic control of the generators connected to S1 position control and to S1, S2 generators

Why is the stability of this configuration?

A small mechanical movement easily destroys the sorter configuration. For a real prototype we will need to take care of the real stability. The Aperture of a microscope are not meant to be very precise or stable so we will need to redesign them in a real market application

How difficult is it to align the elements?

Since we now know the rotation angle the use of corrector lenses can be used to correct final rotation by a few degree. After initial problems now the whole procedure can be done in 5 minutes.

Are 11 electrodes enough for the S2 elements?

The more the better of course, this increases the useful area. However apparently even with 7 electrodes we get a reasonably good area. We really think that the fine tuning of the electrodes in S2 is sufficient

Rev2: This deliverable reports on the realization and testing of the first electrostatic OAM sorter for electrons. It contains an impressive amount of technological developments and remarkable experimental results.

First of all, the construction of the electrostatic sorter device with electrostatic astigmatism correctors represents an absolute novelty not only from the technological but also from the scientific point of view.

The sorter2 device, of simpler conceptual design, presents the technological novelty of addressing 11 electrodes in an electron microscopy diaphragm holder, a development of general interest in the field of transmission electron microscopy.

The resolution test for OAM measurement proved to be very promising ($2h / 2\pi$ resolution) to reach the resolution of $h / 2\pi$. In addition, when compared to the case of the holographic sorter, the increase in diffraction efficiency is quite evident.

The authors justify lack of resolution by observing that both the shape of the sorter1 tip and the shape of the sorter 2 electrodes can still be optimized, especially for sorter2, where the area of potential interest for phase correction is currently small in size.

The authors determined the phase of the sorter 2 with the TIE method, what do they think about a possible use of the electron holography as an alternative to the TIE for the characterization of the sorter2 at the sample level?

Furthermore, greater precision in determining the distribution of the phase shift produced by sorter 2 in working conditions at SAD level could be of great help.

Unfortunately, electron holography, under standard conditions, cannot provide the information requested.

What do the authors think about the possibility of applying the STEM DPC technique to the study of the phase of sorter 2 in the SAD position?

We accept with pleasure all positive comments and agree that better measuring the phase of Sorter elements is essential. The use of STEM DPC is maybe possible even if the object is in the SAD aperture. In any case we don't have the IDPC attachment in the Titan HOLO and we should use the camera and the barycenter of diffraction instead that makes it less practical.

We will consider this and other proposals like using a biprism in different positions or using a grating in the second SAD aperture.

ANNEX IV: ABBREVIATIONS

SHORT NAME OF PARTICIPANTS

Partner	Country	Short Name
National Research Council (Project scientific coordinator)	Italy	CNR
Forschungszentrum Jülich, Ernst Ruska-Centre for Microscopy and Spectroscopy with Electrons	Germany	FZJ
FEI - Thermo Fisher Scientific	The Netherlands	FEI
The Max Planck Institute for the Science of Light	Germany	MPI
University of Glasgow, Department of Physics and Astronomy	United Kingdom	UG
QED Film & Stage Productions Ltd.	United Kingdom	QED
University of Modena and Reggio Emilia, Department of Physics, Informatics, and Mathematics	Italy	UMR
Maastricht University, Maastricht MultiModal Molecular Imaging Institute	The Netherlands	MU

LIST OF ABBREVIATIONS

Consortium Agreement	CA
Description of Action	DoA
Description of Work	DoW
European Commission	EC
Grant Agreement	GA
Kick-off Meeting	KoM
Project Management Board	PMB
Work Package	WP
Work Package Leader	WPL